

SMS CO-DESIGN PLATFORM ON LIVING LABS & LIGHTHOUSES

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ABBREVIATIONS

D	Deliverable
EU	European Union
LH	Light House
LL	Living Lab
NGO	Non-governmental organization
SMS	Soil Mission Support

1 NOTE

Deliverable 4.2 is the SMS Co-Design platform on the Internet. (<https://www.soilmissionsupport.eu>). According to the project application, a separate report on the SMS Co-design platform is not planned. This report only serves to provide some background information about the platform.

2 SMS CO-DESIGN PLATFORM ON LIVING LABS & LIGHTHOUSES

The SMS platform is an interactive knowledge hub and aims to support the mission for soil health and food. It focuses on integrated knowledge on soil health, combining insights from different disciplines and sectors, and showcasing lighthouses and living labs.

The SMS project website (<https://www.soilmissionsupport.eu>) has established itself as a portal to support EU Soil Mission among users already during the project period. The SMS platform will therefore continue to operate under this address in 2023. Now that the SMS project has come to an end, the focus of the website has shifted from the content of the project to the products of the SMS platform. This shift in focus is now graphically visible on the SMS platform.

The platform is easy to use and clearly presents knowledge about soil and land management. It contains examples of lighthouses and living laboratories in this field.

Future integration of the SMS co-design platform with the PrepSoil and JRC's EUSO platforms will ensure sustainability in terms of long-term information provision and production.

The co-design platform for Living Labs and Lighthouses consists of four sections: An introduction to the concept of Living Labs and Lighthouses, their presentation on an interactive map, a search engine for their outputs such as brochures, videos, online tools, as well as an animated film about LL & LH.

3 WHAT ARE LIVING LABS & LIGHTHOUSES?

3.1 Background to living labs & lighthouses

The main goal of the Mission 'A Soil Deal for Europe' is to establish 100 living labs and lighthouses to lead the transition towards healthy soils by 2030. Emerging questions in this context are:

- What are living labs and lighthouses in the context of the soil mission? How can they be defined?
- How are living labs and lighthouses identified, quality checked and documented?

Living labs (LL) and lighthouses (LH) will be selected through competitive calls for proposals under the Horizon Europe R&D programme, following in-depth engagement sessions to build stakeholders' understanding and ownership of these criteria.

It can be expected that first LL & LH nominations based on the Horizon Europe R&I programme will exist as of September 2022 and that nominations will grow continuously.

In the meantime, the SMS project has carried out extensive research to identify already existing projects, which meet the criteria for LL & LH as far as possible (D2.2, Wall et al., 2021; D3.1, Maring et al., 2021; D3.4, Maring et al., 2021).

3.2 LL & LH definition according to Mission Implementation Plan

Living labs are collaborative initiatives to co-create knowledge and innovations while lighthouses are places for demonstration of solutions and exemplary achievements.

More precisely, for the purpose of this mission:

- "Soil health living labs (SH LL)" are defined as "user-centred, place-based and transdisciplinary research and innovation ecosystems, which involve land managers, scientists and other relevant partners in systemic research and co-design, testing, monitoring and evaluation of solutions, in real-life settings, to improve their effectiveness for soil health and accelerate adoption". These living labs are collaborations between multiple partners and coordinate experiments on several sites within a regional or sub-regional area (or working landscapes);
- "Lighthouses" are defined as "places for demonstration of solutions, training and communication that are exemplary in their performance in terms of soil health improvement". They are local sites (one farm, one forest exploitation, one industrial site, one urban city, etc.) that can be included in a living lab area or be situated outside a living lab area.

3.3 Criteria according to Mission Implementation Plan

The implementation plan of the EU Mission "A soil deal for Europe" (EC, 2021) proposes a set of criteria, or rather characteristics, to describe SH LL & LH (figure 2). They are categorized in: AIMS, ACTIVITIES, PARTICIPANTS, CONTEXT (Steen and Van Bueren, 2017, McPhee et al, 2021). Key criteria are:

- the co-creation for soil health and related ecosystem services,
- the widening of societal involvement to contribute to the achievement of all mission objectives,
- that experimentation and innovation should take place in real conditions (e.g. on real farms, contaminated sites, degraded peatlands, city parks).

These criteria imply that living labs supported under the mission would aim at co-creating innovations for soil health and related ecosystem services (e.g. food, climate, biodiversity) and at widening societal involvement

to contribute to the achievement of all mission objectives. Their activities should include co-design and development of practices alongside research on the impact of these practices on ecosystems and the various actors at various scales (including economic and social impacts), networking, knowledge exchange and demonstration. A core criterion for the mission board is that real soil managers should be at the centre of the innovation process and that experimentation and innovation should take place in real conditions (e.g. on real farms, contaminated sites, degraded peatlands, city parks). Beyond soil managers, the living labs should engage with the local authorities, NGOs, the wider public and the policy arena, the EIP-AGRI network and actors at local sites funded under other Horizon Europe Missions to create synergies and promote good practices. The presence of living labs and lighthouses in a region should also be a key enabler of good citizen engagement activities. The approach taken should be open, place-based, involve multiple disciplines (including a strong role for social and behavioural sciences and arts and humanities), multiple methods, and cover multiple dimensions simultaneously (technical, economic, social, and cultural).

As lighthouses are sites achieving exemplary performance in terms of soil health improvement, criteria for selecting them will be based on the mission objectives, indicators and thresholds as defined by the monitoring programme. While we expect to have at least one lighthouse in every living lab area, activities will allow to enrol lighthouses that are outside living lab areas. They will be included in the activities of the European network of LL and LH and will contribute to enhance territorial coverage.

3.4 LL & LH definition developed by SMS project

For LL, there are many definitions, or merely descriptions given in literature and by different initiatives. The definition proposed by the SMS project is based on the Mission Implementation Plan: “Living Labs are spaces for co-innovation through participatory, transdisciplinary and systemic research (Liedtke et al., 2015). Some of these living labs are more mature, they serve as places for demonstration of solutions, training and communication. For these, different terminology exists (pilots, flagships, lighthouses)”.

4 WORK FLOW FOR THE IDENTIFICATION AND DISPLAY OF LL AND LH

4.1 Collection of LL & LH candidates

Figure 3 presents the different steps towards identifying LL & LH and displaying them on a map. The collection of LL & LH candidates was based on the SMS definition of LL & LH (first step). The process of collection was undertaken in three different ways:

- It was based on the overview of LL & LH prepared by the European Mission Board for Soil Health and Food (version Dec 2020).
- Projects implemented in Horizon 2020 and in the European Innovation Partnership “Agricultural productivity and sustainability” were consulted and selected if fitting the SMS definition of LL&LH.
- Further LLs & LHs were collected on search engines by using keyword on Living Labs and, or Lighthouses, and long-term observatories and also by compiling a list of self-declared LL&LH.

4.2 Quality check

The list of living labs identified in the collection phase was then subjected to a validation process based on the 4 main criteria of living labs according to the Mission Plan implementation (figure 2). The validation process was performed through a desk study.

A point of attention is that in some cases, the availability of information on the LL/LH was poor and the

language used to report the LL/LH was unknown to the person in charge of the validation. The exercise considers what information on existing LL and LH can be retrieved within a reasonable amount of effort, to perform this validation. For example, in “context”, the multiple dimensions that should be covered (technical, economic, social) are quite important to determine if the LL has a sufficiently broad approach, but it was hard to find this information in many of the public descriptions, which in many cases just mention the topics that are covered in the LL. In this case, it is presumed that this aspect is already sufficiently reflected by the other fields such as “activities” and involved “participants”.

4.3 Current state - input data by September 2022

An updated excel list of potential LLs & LHs candidates is available after a quality check of the collected LL & LH by the European Mission board for Soil Health and Food and the SMS project. In total, the list contains currently 163 entries of LLs & LHs (version September 2022). Each LL & LH is indexed with the following information:

- Whether it is a LL or a LH or both
- Name and short summary of the project
- Land use the LL/LH addresses (farms, forests, nature, industrial areas and urban settings)
- Country/countries in which the LL/LH is/are located
- Geographic coordinates

It should be noted that there is still a lot of “noise” in this overall list, while the entries have not all been validated according to the characteristics as proposed for LL & LH (Figure 2). It can be assumed, that many people that have marked their initiative as a LL or LH and that have ended up in this list, have a different understanding on definitions.

It should be stressed that this current list is rather a candidate list for living labs and lighthouses and needs further validation, which will be done in the framework of PREPSOIL (Preparing for the Soil Deal for Europe Mission), the SMS successor project.

5 CO-DESIGNED MAP OF LIVING LABS & LIGHTHOUSES

5.1 Functionality of interactive map

The Living Labs and Lighthouses map shows the entries in all their different variations and characteristics. A distinction is made between Living Labs and Lighthouses. All entries can be filtered by different criteria, e.g. thematic criteria like agricultural or urban LLs or LHs. In addition, a selection specifically for EU-funded LLs and LHs is possible. Usually, Living Labs consist of several subunits. Therefore, Living Labs that belong together are highlighted in colour and are connected by a line. By clicking on the flag, more information about the respective LLs and LHs can be obtained.

Map of Living Labs and Lighthouses

Read more about LL & LH

Please select:

- All (170)
- Living labs (111)
- Lighthouses (59)

Filter for LL & LH:

- Agriculture (106)
- Forestry (15)
- Urban (36)
- Protected areas (9)
- Industry (5)
- Infrastructure (2)
- Other (11)

Filter by Funding:

- All (170)
- EU funded (0)
- others (170)

Submit

5.2 IT Specifications

The SMS-platform can be found at the address <https://www.soilmissionsupport.eu/living-labs-lighthouses> and is currently hosted on the web server of the Environment Agency Austria. With the help of the content management system Typoo-3, the graphical and textual content can be easily updated and changed at any time.

The two internet applications - Map of LL & LH and Products of LL & LH - are stand-alone JavaScript applications that have been integrated into the platform. For technical reasons they are not editable via Typoo-3. They were deliberately programmed in simple script languages to allow easy transfer to future platforms (EUSO, Prepsoil). The selected script languages HTML and Javascript are universally used languages and are accepted resp. executed by every internet browser.

In addition to the two script languages, the map module leaflet, which is freely available as open source, is used for the map of LL & LH. Leaflet uses openstreetmap (also open source) to create online maps with any zoom level. Leaflet is also programmed in Javascript and is accepted by every browser. It can be easily integrated into any HTML/Javascript application - so also into the map of LL & LH.

This deliberate reduction to universally used programming languages has the advantage that the whole application can be easily transferred to any other technical platform and environment.

5.3 Option for new LL & LH data

The information about the approximately 180 living labs and lighthouses is stored in a separate Javascript data file. (<https://www.soilmissionsupport.eu/fileadmin/inhalte/soilmission/map/js/data.js>). This text-based file can be opened and edited in any word processing program. New LLs & LHs can be easily added and existing LLs & LHs can be changed at any time considering the given data structure.

5.4 Sustainability beyond SMS Project

The interactive map to the LL & LH has been developed in close collaboration with colleagues from the JRC (Mark van Liedekerke, Arwyn Jones). On the date of completion of the Soil Mission Support project, the map of living labs and lighthouses has been transferred to the Joint Research Center's Earth Observatory Platform (EUSO) and the follow-up project "PrepSoil". The map of living labs and lighthouse runs now in parallel under <https://prepsoil.eu/living-labs-and-lighthouses/map>.

6 CO-DESIGNED PRODUCT ARCHIVE OF LIVING LABS AND LIGHTHOUSES

Living Labs and Lighthouses produced many outputs, which were identified by the SMS project and displayed on the platform. These products are non-peer-reviewed innovative knowledge (e.g. brochures, videos, guidance documents, teaching materials, maps). A search engine guides the user through this archive.

Home / Living labs & lighthouses / Products

Living lab & lighthouse products

Living Labs and Lighthouses produced many outputs which were identified by the SMS project and displayed on this website. These products are non-peer-reviewed innovative knowledge (e.g. brochures, videos, guidance documents, teaching materials, maps).

Search by keyword:

Set filters by categories (optional):

Agriculture Forest Urban Protected areas Industry Other

Set filters by media type (optional):

Text Video Presentation Poster Graphic Online tool

AGROMIX - Handbook of resilience and working definitions

The AGROMIX project aims at building a practical framework of attributes that would guide farmers to recognize and

Link: <https://www.soilmissionsupport.eu/products>

This archive reflects a comprehensive research of the products (brochures, videos, etc.) of the Living Lab and Light House candidates in the current database of the SMS platform.

Due to the unfortunately small number of products for LL and LH, the H2020 projects presented at the Soil Cluster Day 2021 organised by the SMS project were also researched and their products included.

7 FILM ON LIVING LABS AND LIGHTHOUSES

In terms of LL&LH, the short animated film completes the platform very well. Further explanations of the film can be found in the CDE plan of the SMS project (D4.5).

Link: <https://www.soilmissionsupport.eu/film>